

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TABLET LAXMIVILAS RASA IN AMAVATA DISEASE- A
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ABSTRACT

Amavata is the most common endogenous disease which is produced due to frequently formation of Ama in the human body. It is the commonest among chronic inflammatory joint disease in which joints become swollen, painful & stiff. Laxmivilas Rasa, an ancient Ayurvedic polyherbal and mineral formulation, has been mention in Classic and also applying for centuries to manage Amavata. This classical formulation, composed many ingredient which effectively mange the symptoms of Amavata like Pain, Swelling or Doshik imbalance in our body. This research paper delves into the pharmacological properties, pharmacokinetics, and pharmacodynamics of Tablet Laxmivilas Rasa, emphasizing its therapeutic potential in Amavata. We provide a critical analysis of how its key ingredients function synergistically reduce the symptoms of Amavata. Furthermore, this paper discusses the safety profile and toxicity considerations, particularly regarding the heavy metals present in the formulation, and underscores the importance of following traditional purification methods. Clinical studies highlight its effects in Amavata.

KEYWORDS: Laxmivilas Rasa, Amavata, Ayurveda, Herbo-mineral formulations, Pharmacokinetics, Pharmacodynamics.**INTRODUCTION**

The ancient record of Ayurveda mentions several treatments for a disease, while one formulation has multiple indications. Laxmi villas rasa has indicated for Many diseases. Laxmivilas Rasa is one of such herbo-mineral combination indicated in Kustha (diseases of skin), Prameh (urinary disorders), Nadvrana (sinus), Arsha (piles), Bhagandara (fistulka in-ano), Shlipada (filariasis), Atisara (diarrhea), Amavata (rheumatism), Udararog (diseases of abdomen), Kasa (cough), Rajyakshma (tuberculosis), Sthoulya (obesity), Sula (pain), Shirorog (diseases of head) and Strirog (gynecological disorders). This formulation mainly acts as Kapha-Vataghna and widely used in treating Dushta-Pratishyaya (chronic rhinitis). Amavata is the most common endogenous disease which is produced due to frequently formation of Ama in the human body. It is the commonest among chronic inflammatory joint disease in

which joints become swollen, painful & stiff due to imbalance of Vata-Kapha dosha. Use of Laxmivillas in Amavata as two modes of treatment: Dosha-Pratyani (this therapy focuses on correcting the root cause of disease by bringing the vitiated doshas, e.g., Vata, Pitta, and Kapha) and Vyadhi-Pratyani (this method focuses directly on combating the specific disease entity or symptom).

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- To review disease Aamvata from various Ayurvedic Samhitas.
- To review the pharmacological properties, pharmacokinetics, and pharmacodynamics of Tablet Laxmivilas Rasa.
- To review the effect of Laxmivilas Rasa in Amavata.

Amavata

Due to mandagni, Aahara rasa remains in apakwa avastha and it gradually forms Ama in the body. It leads to prakopa of all doshas. Amavata is characterised by pain, stiffness, swelling affecting various joints of the body accompanied by range of non-articular features such as body ache, anorexia, malaise, etc.^[1]

Etiology (Nidan) of Amavata^[2]

Indulgence in incompatible eatables and habits, lack of physical activity, or doing exercise after taking fatty eatables and those who have poor digestive capacity even normally also generate āma (improperly digested eatable) in the body. When a person of sedentary habits with a poor digestive faculty indulges in incompatible diet and regimen, or does physical exercise after taking fatty food the ama is formed. This āma, associating itself with vāta, moves quickly to the different seats of kapha in the body filling them and the dhamañis (blood vessels) with waxy material. Thus, the abnormal end product of digestion associated with vāta, pitta and kapha assuming different colours, blocks the tissue pores and passages with thick waxy material. It renders the patient weak in no time and produces a feeling of heaviness in the pericardial region. This substance named ama is the cause of so many distressing diseases. When provoked āma simultaneously afflicts the pelvic and shoulder, they girdle and make other joints of the body stiff. This condition has been identified as Amavāta.

In Madhav Nidana, Madhukosha mentions for the first time the main five causes for the manifestation of Amavata disease.^[2]

Viruddhahara: Viruddha refers to foods that typically challenge the system and are inappropriate for the body's normal Dhatu (tissue elements) and Doshas. This Viruddha Ahara is the most frequent etiological cause of the majority of disorders, much like Amavata.

Viruddha Cheshta: Hindered activities, because they vitiate Agni, which leads to the formation of Ama, are the main cause of the disease's manifestation.

Mandagni: Slowness or inactive in the digestive mechanism which can cause a number of illnesses.

Nischalata: Physical inactivity and a sedentary lifestyle contribute to an increase in Kapha, which results in Agnimandya and subsequently leads to the formation of Ama.

Doing exercise after taking snigdha ahara**Pathogenesis of Amavata^[3]**

As discussed earlier whenever the function of Agni is disturbed in the body Ama is produced. This produced Ama is slimy in nature, such Ama get together with Dushit Vata / Prakopit Vata and circulates all over the body through Shira and Dhamani and gets lodged in

Kaphasthana i.e. Sandhi because Shleshak Kapha is located in Sandhi and Amvata is developed.

Samprapti Ghataka

- Dosha - Vata pradhan tridosha
- Dooshya - Rasadi dhatu; Asthigata snayu; Sira
- Agni - Jatharagni; Rasadhatwagni
- Ama - Jatharagnijanya & Rasadhatwagnijanya
- Srotas - Rasavaha, Asthivaha
- Udbhava Sthana - Amashaya
- Adhishthan - Asthisandhi
- Rogamarga - Madhyama

Cardinal sign and Symptom of Amavata.^[4]

General signs and symptom of Amavata are body ache, anorexia, thirst, heaviness, fever and numbness.

Sign and Symptoms of advanced Amavata^[4]

- Painful Swelling of the hand, feet, ankle, hip joints and spine.
- Nature of pain is like that of scorpion sting,
- Stiffness
- Hindered digestive mechanism
- Excessive salivation
- Anorexia
- Heaviness
- Lack of enthusiasm
- Distaste in the mouth
- Burning sensation
- Excessive urination
- Hardness and pain in the abdomen
- Disturbed sleep
- Thirst
- Vertigo
- Fainting
- Stiffness in precordium
- Constipation
- Stiffness
- Intestinal sounds
- Distension of abdomen
- Severe difficulties with complications

Laxmivilas Rasa

Laxmivilas Rasa is a herbo mineral formulation. Combination of herbal and mineral drugs has increased the shelf life and efficacy of the formulation, Laxmivilas Rasa has a wide range of indication in various Roga (Disease). This formulation mainly acts on Kapha Vataj Roga as compared to Pittaj Roga as this formulation has many Ushna Virya (hot potency) Dravya. Various formulations mentioned under the name Laxmivilas Rasa. These formulations should be taken into consideration as alternative formulations for choosing the most appropriate combination of Laxmivilas Rasa based on the patient's condition and symptoms of disease because they differ in a few constituents, which alters their therapeutic efficacy. Such formulations are depicted in table 1.

Table 1: Showing various references quoted indifferent Ayurvedic text.^[5]

SI NO	Name of the Author	Formulations
1.	Bhaishajya Ratnavali	
2.	Vaidya Chintamani	Suvarna Bhasma, Rajat Bhasma, Tamra Bhasma, Kanta Loha, Mandur Bhasma, Abhrak Bhasma, Vanga Bhasma, Naga Bhasma, Praval, Mukta Bhasma, Parad Bhasma.
3.	Yaga Ratnakar	Kanta Loha, Abhrak Satva, Tamra, Suvarna, Vanga, Rajat, Naga, Praval, Mukta, Parad Bhasma
4.	Rasa Pradhan	Parad, Loha, Abhrak, Gandhak, Rajat, Suvarna
5.	Rasayana Sangraha	Parad, Suvaran, Hirak, Praval, Mukta, Abhrak, Naga, Vanga, Kanta Loha, Tamra.

Physicians frequently use another formulation called Naradiya Laxmivilas, in addition to all the other formulations.

Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Rasayana Adhikara 55 - 68)^[6]

Table 2: Showing Ingredient name and Quantity of Naradiya Laxmivillas.

SN	Ingredients	Latin Name	Quantity
1.	<i>Abhraka Bhasma</i>	Purified and processed Mica	40 g.
2.	<i>Shuddha Parada</i>	Purified Mercury	20 g.
3.	<i>Shuddha Gandhaka</i>	Purified Sulphur	20 g.
4.	<i>Karpoora</i>	Cinnamomum camphora	20 g.
5.	<i>Jatiphala</i>	Myristica fragrans	20 g.
6.	<i>Jatikosha</i>	Nutmeg	20 g.
7.	<i>Vridhdhadaru</i>	Argyrea speciosa	10 g.
8.	<i>Dhattura</i>	Datura metel	10 g.
9.	<i>Bhanga</i>	Cannabis sativa	10 g.
10.	<i>Vidarikanda</i>	Pueraria tuberosa	10 g.
11.	<i>Shatavari</i>	Asparagus racemosus	10 g.
12.	<i>Nagabala</i>	Grewia populifolia	10 g.
13.	<i>Atibala</i>	Abutilon indicum	10 g.
14.	<i>Gokshura</i>	Tribulus terrestris	10 g.
15.	<i>Nichula</i>	Strychnos nux vomica	10 g.
16.	<i>Nagavalli</i>	Piper betel	Q.S.

Dose of Laxmivilas Rasa^[6]: 250 mg

General Indications of Laxmivilas Rasa^[7]

Six of the seven formulations contain a mix of mercury and sulphur, according to the data analysis. Although Laxmivilas Rasa is primarily used to treat Shiroroga, Swasa, Kasa, and Rajayakshma, other formulations of

the same name that are cited in different texts include diseases such as Kustha, Prameha, Nadvirana, Arsha, Bhagandara, Shlipada, Atisara, Amavata, Udararog, Sthoulya, Shula, Strirog, Jwara, and Vataroga. The Indian Ayurvedic formulary contained Laxmivilas Rasa from Bhaishajya Ratnavali.^[6]

Indication of Laxmivilas of Different Author

Table 3: Showing various Indication quoted in different Ayurvedic text.^[5]

SI NO	Name of the Author	Indication
1.	Bhaishajya Ratnavali	Kustha, Prameha, Nadvirana, Arsha, Bhagandara, Shlipada, Atisara, Amavata, Udararog, Kasa, Rajyakshma, Sthoulya, sula, Shirorog, Strirog
2.	Vaidya Chintamani	Rajaroga, Pandu, Chardi Roga, Shwas, Kasa, Kamala, Dhirkagalini Vataroga, 5 Types of Gulma, All Types of Shula, Unmada, Mathi Bransha, 8 Types of Udara, Maharoga, 20 Types of Prameha, Shandata, Aruchi, Mandagni, Grahani, Vali, Palita, Kampavata.
3.	Yaga Ratnakar	8 Maharog, Prameha, Kshay, Pandu, Kamala, Naste Indriya, Chira Atisaar, Mutra Krich, Gar, Shosha, Vali Palitha, Krushatha.
4.	Rasa Pradhan	5 Types of Kasa, Pandu, Hikka, Rajyakshma, Vayu, Halimak, Apasmar.
5.	Rasayana Sangraha	Prameha, Kasa, Vrana, Pandu, Hikka, Mahashula, Mandagni, Kapha-Vataja Rog, Apasmaar, Kustha, Halimak, Jwar.

DISCUSSION

Laxmivilas Rasa is a herbo-mineral combination and contains several micronutrients, which play a key part in providing relief from difficulties of Amavata. Numerous important components directly affect Amavata, while

numerous other components aid in correcting Doshik imbalance and direct effect on other internal mechanisms like digestion etc... After understanding the medicinal effects of each of Laxmivilas Rasa's constituent elements, it can be easily understood.

Table 4: Consist of Pharmacological Properties, action and Indication of the common ingredients.

SL.NO	Name of Ingredient	Pharmacological Properties	Action on Dosha	Action	Indications
1.	<i>Krishnabhrak Bhasma (Mica)</i> ^[8,9]	Madhur, Snigdha Shita Virya	Tridosha	Vrushya Ayushya, Balya, Ruchikar, Deepan, Dattu Vrudhikar	Kshay, Pandu, Shula, Kustha, Jwar, Shwasa, Prameha, Aruchi, Kasa, Udar Roga.
2.	<i>Shuddha Gandhak (Sulphur)</i> ^[8,9]	Katu, Kashaya, Tikta, Ushna Virya, Madhur Vipak	Kaph-Vata	Rashyan, Deepan, Pachana	Krimi, Kandu, Kustha, Visarpa, Dadru, Kshya, Pleeharoga, Visahara
3.	<i>Suddha Parad (Mercury)</i> ^[8]	Sadrasa, Singdha	Tridosha	Rasayana, Yogavahi	Sarva Ragahara
4.	<i>Jaipal (Nutmeg)</i> ^[10]	Tikta, Katu, Laghu, Tikshna, Ushna, virya	Kapha - Vata	Rocaka Agnidipak Grahi, Stambhan	Krimi, Kasa, Vaman, Swasa, Sosha, Peenas, Hdrog
5.	<i>Chandra (Karpura) Cinnamomum camphora (Nees & Eberm)</i> ^[11]	Madhur, tikta Laghu	Kapha – Pitta	Vrushya, Chakshushya Lekhana	Daha, Trushna, Asyavairasya, Meda daurgandhya nashaka
6.	<i>Jatikosha (Javitri) Myristica Fragrans (Houtt)</i> ^[12]	Katu, Laghu, Ushna virya	Kapha har	Rucya, varnakrita	Kasa, Vaman, Swasa, Trishna, Krimi, Vishavikar
7.	<i>Vrddhadaraka bija (Ipomoeapetaloidia Chois)</i> ^[13]	Kasaya, Katu, Tikta, Sarak Ushna virya	Kapha	Rasayan, Vrisya, balya Swara kar	Amavata, Shotha, Arsha, Prameha
8.	<i>Gokshur (Puncture Vine)</i> ^[14]	Madhur Rasa, Shita Virya	Vata Hara	Deepan, Vrushya, Pustikarak	Ashmari, Prameha, Shwas, Kasa, Arsha, Mutrakruccha, Hrudroga
9.	<i>Dhattura bija (Datura metel Linn)</i> ^[15]	Kasaya, madhur, Tikta, Guru Ushna virya	Kapha	Mada, varna, Jatharagni vardhaka	Jwara, Kushtha, Kandu, Krimi, Vishavikar
10.	<i>Vidarimula (Pueraria tuberosa DC.)</i> ^[16]	Madhur, snigdha, Brihana, Guru, Sitavirya	Pitta-Vata	Stanya, Sukral, Swarya, Mutral	Karshya
11.	<i>Shatavari (Asparagus)</i> ^[17]	Guru, Shita, Tikta, Madhur	Vata-Pitta -Rakta	Medhya, Agni Vardhak, Pusti Dhayak, Snigdha, Netrya, Balya, Shukrala Stanya Kari, Hrudya, Vrushya, Rasayani	Gulma, Atisaar, Shotha, Arsha, Grahani, Kshay
12.	<i>Atibala</i> ^[18] (Country Mallow)	Madhur Rasa, Shita Virya	Vata	Rasayan, Balya, Kranti Kruta, Mutrajnan, Mrudu Rechan, Vajikaran	Prameha, Mutra Kruchha, Jwar, Rakta Pradar, Arsha
13.	<i>Naga bala</i> ^[19] (Snake Mallow)	Madhur Rasa, Shita Virya	Vata	Mutrajnan, Rasayan	Garbini Atisara, Mutra kriccha, Varna

					Balya, Jwaragna, Visham Jwar
14.	<i>Nagavali</i> ^[20] (<i>Betel Leaf</i>)	Tikta, Katu, Ushna, Laghu, Kshar	Rakta Pitta Kara, Kapha Vata Hara	Ruchya, Sara, Balyandhya Hara, Shrama Hara	Mukha Dourgandhya Hara, Shrama Hara
15.	<i>Bhanga Beej</i> ^[21] (<i>IndianHemp</i>)	Tikta Ushna Virya Lagu, Tikсна	Kapha	Grahi, Pachaka, Vedhna Hara	Suryavata, Apatantral, Nidranash, Sagrahani, Atisaar, Visuchika, Kasa, Aamvata
16.	<i>Kuchala</i> ^[22] (<i>Nux Vomica</i>)	Tikta Rasa, Shita Virya, Laghu	Vata Vardhak, Kapha Pitta Rakta Nashak	Madha Karak, Vyatha Hara, Grahi	Vata Roga, Shya Mutra, Krimi Vrana

Here we can see the range of therapeutic utility of ingredients of Laxmivilas Rasa. Laxmivilas Rasa is Kapha-Vatahara in action although its ingredients such as Abhraka bhasma, Gandhaka, Parada, Shatavari and Atibala have properties to cure nearly all diseases. The ingredients are mostly Ushnavirya, hence this formula have limitations in Pitta vitiated conditions. According to a pharmacodynamic point of view, Laxmivilas Rasa helps to neutralize or destroy vitiated Kapha and Vata and reestablish the formation and function of Prakruta Vata and Kapha, which play a good role in Amavata. It can be interpreted that Laxmivilas Rasa acts as Vedana naska (painkiller) with the help of some ingredients like Dhatura and Kuchila and ultimately cures those diseases. Many other ingredients in Laxmivilas Rasa promote Deepan and Pachan, which help digest properly and minimise the Ama formation in our bodies. Bhanga Beej is directly used in Amavata Chikitsa. Combination of other ingredients Laxmivilas rasa helps to reduce other vitals symptoms of Amavata disease. Above mentioned research works on individual ingredients of Laxmivilas Rasa have some limitations as drug action changes with change in combination of other drugs. In this case, it can be discovered that the combination of many medications in Laxmivilas Rasa improves its efficacy and safety while also contributing to both significant and modest advantages in the treatment of Amavata.

CONCLUSIONS

The literature makes it evident that Amavata has been treated with Laxmivilas Rasa. In conclusion, Laxmivilas Rasa is still a useful tool for treating Amavata in both traditional Ayurvedic therapy and possibly modern integrative medicine. To further confirm its safety and effectiveness and investigate its potential uses in the treatment of Amavata, more clinical study is required.

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